

GANDBOLDA OTISH TEZLIGI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING AHAMIYATI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589837>

Alimardon Choriyev Farxodovich

Buxoro Davlat Universiteti Pedagogika institutining

Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi uslubiyoti kafedrası

1-bosqich magistri

Annatatsiya: *Gandbolda jamoaviy sport turida maksimal kuch, kuch, tezlik, chidamlilik va tortishish tezligi kabi xususiyatlar ustunlik qiladi, yakuniy maqsad raqibga qaraganda ko'proq gol urishdir. Gol urish va g'alaba qozonish usuli samarali tortishish ko'rsatkichidir. Ushbu sharhning maqsadi so'nggi o'n yil ichida gandbolda o'q otish tezligi bo'yicha nashrlarni o'rganish, o'q otish tezligi tushunchasi va uni rivojlantirish uchun tavsiya etilgan o'quv dasturlarining ahamiyatini o'rganishdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *O'q Otish Tezligi, Gandbol, Zarba Berish, Otish Texnikasi*

Kirish

Jamoaviy sport turi bo'lgan gandbolda mashg'ulot va musobaqa paytida zo'ravon aloqalarga va qisqa / yuqori intensivlikdagi jismoniy harakatlarga qarshi tura oladigan jismoniy kuch qobiliyatiga ega bo'lish kerak. Raqobat paytida yuzlab marta yuqori intensiv jismoniy faoliyatni boshdan kechirish holati yuqori darajadagi kuch talablarini, shuningdek, egalik qilgan kuchni uzoq muddatli saqlashni talab qiladi. Maksimal kuch, kuch, tezlik, chidamlilik va olov tezligi; elita bu darajadagi o'ynagan gandbolda muvaffaqiyat qozonish uchun zarur bo'lgan asosiy omillardan biridir.²

Tortishish asosiy qobiliyat bo'lsa-da, unga tortishish samaradorligi jihatidan "tortishish tezligi" va "urish" kabi ikkita asosiy omil ta'sir qiladi. Gandbolda muvaffaqiyatli bo'lgan zarbalarni tahlil qilishda zarbalar tezligi ularning aniqligi bilan birga birlashtiriladi uni baholash kerakligi tushuniladi. Tabiiyki, o'yinchining bu kuchi zarba paytida hosil bo'ladigan yong'in tezligiga ham ta'sir qiladi. Shu bilan birga, o'yinchining to'pni tasarruf etish qobiliyati bu zarba tezligi bilan bevosita bog'liq. Ammo tortishish qo'lining kuchi nafaqat yuqori oyoq bilan bog'liq; tortishish texnikasi, uning davomida tana qismlarining uyg'unligiva uni pastki ekstremitalarning kuchi bilan birgalikda baholash kerak.³

² Aloui, G., Hermassi, S., Hammami, M., Gaamouri, N., Comfort, P., Shephard, R. J., Schwesig, R. ve Chelly, M. S. (2019). Effects of an 8-week in-season upper limb elastic band training programme on the peak power, strength, and throwing velocity of junior handball players. *Sportverletzung Sportschaden*, 33(3), 133-141.

³ Andersson, S. H., Bahr, R., Clarsen, B. ve Myklebust, G. (2017). Preventing overuse shoulder injuries among throwing athletes: a cluster-randomised controlled trial in 660 elite handball players. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 51(14), 1073-1080.

Yurak urishini rivojlantirish bo'yicha turli xil o'quv dasturlarini amalga oshirish adabiyotda ta'kidlangan masaladir. Bu borada qarshilik ko'rsatish bo'yicha o'quv dasturlari birinchi o'ringa chiqadi. Gandbolda asosiy maqsad raqibga qaraganda ko'proq gol urishdir. Gol urish va g'alaba qozonish usuli samarali tortishish ko'rsatkichidir. Samarali tortishish uchun katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan tortishish tezligi tushunchasi ko'p yillar davomida tadqiqot mavzusi bo'lib kelgan; shuningdek, bu gandbol murabbiylari, sportchilar va olimlar uchun zarur bo'lgan mavzu.⁴

Otish Texnikasi

Qadam bosishdan keyin sodir bo'ladigan sakrash va ushlab turish bosqichi tufayli gorizontal tezlikni oshirib, gorizontal tezlik oshadi, bu esa mudofaaning zarbaga xalaqit berish ehtimolini kamaytiradi va zarba tezligini oshiradi. Qal'aning markaziga qarab harakatlanish natijasida sodir bo'lgan zarbalar yuqori tezlikka ega; ammo, tortishish tezligiga qadam va tos-magistral harakati ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi ayon bo'ladi qo'yildi.⁵

Yelka Kuchi

Gandbol-bu boshning tepasidan (tepadan) zarbalar kuchli bo'lgan va sportchi o'yin davomida 100 ga yaqin pas va zarbalardan foydalanadigan sport turi. Otish paytida barcha bosqichlarda elkaning ichki va tashqi rotatorlari konsentrik/eksantrik ravishda bo'ladi ishlatiladi. Boshqa tomondan, shikastlanish xavfi va uzoq reabilitatsiya davriga ega bo'lgan elka sohasi sportchida surunkali og'riq va azob-uqubatlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu muammoga duch kelgan gandbolchi tabiiy ravishda urish va tortishish tezligi jihatidan ham muammolarga duch kelishi mumkin..⁶

Yadro va kuchni qo'llash va mashg'ulotlar

Gandbolda zarbaning samaradorligi ko'p jihatdan zarbaning tezligi va aniqligiga bog'liq. Mavzu bilan bog'liq tadqiqotlar o'rganilganda, noyabr darajasi tushunchasi pastki va yuqori ekstremitalarning mushaklarini muvofiqlashtirish va maksimal portlovchi kuch bilan birlashtirilganligi ta'kidlandi. Ushbu yo'nalishda yurak urishi va aniqligini oshirish uchun ba'zi o'qitish usullaridan foydalanish majburiy bo'lib qoldi. Gandbolda noyabr oyi uchun mushaklarning, ayniqsa qorin, paraspinal va gluteal mintaqalarda joylashgan mushaklarning rivojlanishi juda muhimdir.⁷

Qarshilik tasma-sini tayyorlashni qo'llash

⁴ Chelly, M. S., Hermassi, S. ve Shephard, R. J. (2010). Relationships between power and strength of the upper and lower limb muscles and throwing velocity in male handball players. *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 24, 1480–1487.

⁵ Debanne, T. ve Laffaye, G. (2013). Coaches' beliefs and knowledge: Training programs used by French professional coaches to increase ball-throwing velocity in elite handball players. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 8(3), 557-570.

⁶ Eriksrud, O., Sæland, F. O., Federolf, P. A. ve Cabri, J. (2019). Functional mobility and dynamic postural control predict overhead handball throwing performance in elite female team handball players. *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 18(1), 91-100.

⁷ García, J. A., Sabido, R., Barbado, D. ve Moreno, F. J. (2013). Analysis of the relation between throwing speed and throwing accuracy in team-handball according to instruction. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 13(2), 149-154.

So'nggi yillarda juda keng qo'llanilgan yana bir material elastik (qarshilik) lentaldir. Ham sportchilar, ham harakatsiz shaxslar uchun qarshilik tasmasi dasturlari ayniqsa, rehabilitatsiya dasturlarida qo'llaniladi. Bundan tashqari, bu sportchilarni yuklashda xavfsiz muhit bilan ta'minlaydigan samarali va arzon usul. Qarshilik tasmagini tayyorlashni tegishli qarshilik va tobora ortib borayotgan yuk muhiti ta'minlangan ekan, sportchining noyabr kuchi va kuchini oshirish usuli deb hisoblaydigan keng tarqalgan fikr mavjud.

Antropometrik Xususiyatlar

Yuqori va pastki ekstremitalar bilan bir qatorda antropometrik tuzilish ham gandbol sportchisida muhim xususiyatdir. Chunki musobaqa davomida huquqbuzarlik nuqtai nazaridan tortishish va mudofaa va tanadan tanaga himoya qilish nuqtai nazaridan bloklar kabi mezonlar jismoniy tuzilishning ahamiyatini oshiradi. Shu bilan birga, iste'dodni tanlash o'zgaruvchisi sifatida ishlatiladigan antropometrik tuzilish ham insonning kuchi va kuchi bilan bog'liq.

Psixologik Holat

To'g'ri mashg'ulot sharoitlarini ta'minlash va sportda ishlashni yaxshilash maqsadida, shuningdek, psixologik holatning roli katta. Xususan, maqsadlarni belgilash, tasavvur qilish, qulaylik, o'z-o'zini gapirish, hissiyotlarni boshqarish va o'ziga ishonch sportdagi psixologik qobiliyat bilan bog'liq. Adabiyotda asosiy mavzusi gandbol va psixologik holat bo'lgan tadqiqotlar soni etarli bo'lmasa-da, otishni o'rganish maxsus psixologik dasturlar yordamida yaxshilanishi ta'kidlangan. Natijada salbiy stimullarni qabul qiluvchi sportchilarning yurak urish tezligida sezilarli o'sish kuzatildi. Shu sababli, sportchilar o'rtasidagi darajadagi farq, sport tarixi va yoshi kabi omillar dek darajasi va samaradorligi bilan aniq bog'liqdir va bu turli tadqiqotlarda ta'kidlangan.⁸

Xulosa Va Tavsiyalar

Gandbolda zarba berish tezligining g'alaba qozonishning asosiy sharti bo'lgan "ko'proq gol urish" maqsadiga erishishdagi o'rni yaqqol ko'rinib turibdi. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, yurak urishi faqat mezon emas, balki u doimo aniqlikka moslashishi kerak. Natijada, gandbolda tortishish tezligi bo'yicha olib boriladigan malakali tadqiqotlar sonining ko'payishi bilan; jins, sportchi darajasi va qo'llaniladigan o'quv protokollarining ta'siri ushbu sohada ishlaydigan tadqiqotchilar va murabbiylar tomonidan qabul qilinadi bundan tashqari, uni ko'rishni osonlashtiradi deb o'ylashadi.

FOYDALANGAN ADABIYOTLAR

⁸ Hermassi, S., Delank, K. S., Fieseler, G., Bartels, T., Chelly, M. S., Khalifa, R., Laudner, K., Schulze, S. ve Schwesig, R. (2019a). Relationships between olympic weightlifting exercises, peak power of the upper and lower limb, muscle volume and throwing ball velocity in elite male handball players. Sportverletzung Sportschaden, 33(2), 104-112.

1. Aloui, G., Hermassi, S., Hammami, M., Gaamouri, N., Comfort, P., Shephard, R. J., Schwesig, R. ve Chelly, M. S. (2019). Effects of an 8-week in-season upper limb elastic band training programme on the peak power, strength, and throwing velocity of junior handball players. *Sportverletzung Sportschaden*, 33(3), 133-141.
2. Andersson, S. H., Bahr, R., Clarsen, B. ve Myklebust, G. (2017). Preventing overuse shoulder injuries among throwing athletes: a cluster-randomised controlled trial in 660 elite handball players. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 51(14), 1073-1080.
3. Chelly, M. S., Hermassi, S. ve Shephard, R. J. (2010). Relationships between power and strength of the upper and lower limb muscles and throwing velocity in male handball players. *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 24, 1480-1487.
4. Debanne, T. ve Laffaye, G. (2013). Coaches' beliefs and knowledge: Training programs used by French professional coaches to increase ball-throwing velocity in elite handball players. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 8(3), 557-570.
5. Eriksrud, O., Sæland, F. O., Federolf, P. A. ve Cabri, J. (2019). Functional mobility and dynamic postural control predict overhead handball throwing performance in elite female team handball players. *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 18(1), 91-100.
6. García, J. A., Sabido, R., Barbado, D. ve Moreno, F. J. (2013). Analysis of the relation between throwing speed and throwing accuracy in team-handball according to instruction. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 13(2), 149-154.
7. Hermassi, S., Delank, K. S., Fieseler, G., Bartels, T., Chelly, M. S., Khalifa, R., Laudner, K., Schulze, S. ve Schwesig, R. (2019a). Relationships between olympic weightlifting exercises, peak power of the upper and lower limb, muscle volume and throwing ball velocity in elite male handball players. *Sportverletzung Sportschaden*, 33(2), 104-112.